

Research in Management and Humanities

DWIJM VOL 2 NO 1 (2023) ISSN: 2980-4817

Available online at www.dwijmh.org
Journal homepage: <http://www.dwijmh.org>

Measuring the Effect of Organizational Climate on the Employees' Work Performance as perceived by the Employees.

Damianus Abun^(a) Marlene T. Nicolas^(b) Eldefonso B. Natividad Jr.^(c)

Winicel May C. Ancheta^(d) Editha B. Acidera^(e) Fredolin P. Julian^(f)

- a) PhD: Professor, School of Business and Accountancy, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.
b) PhD: Dean, School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte Philippines.
c) PhD: Professor, School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.
d) PhD: Professor, School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.
e) EdD: Professor, School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.
f) PhD: Professor: School of Business and Accountancy, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received: January 7, 2023

Received in rev. February 15, 2023

Accepted: March 15, 2023

Keywords:

organizational climate, individual work performance, clarity, contextual performance, counterproductive work behavior.

JEL Classification:

OD23; O15

ABSTRACT

Research in organizational climate paves the way to understanding the work environment. The study explored the effect of organizational climate on the individual work performance of the employees. To deepen the understanding of the concepts of the study, the literature was reviewed. The study used descriptive assessment and correlational research design and used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data. The population included all employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag, hence total enumeration was applied. The study found that all dimensions of organizational climate were high, but not very high, likewise with individual work performance. Analysis of Variance showed a significant correlation between organizational climate and individual work performance.

© 2022 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This article is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Organizational performance is simply the realization of organizational objectives (Abubakar, et.al, 2019). Knowledge management is a strategy to optimize the firm's knowledge economy which includes several elements such as human resources practices, technology, culture, and organizational structures (Du Plessis, 2007). In other words, the management needs to identify the job and the skills required by the job and develop and deploy people to the job which is matched the skills (Qiang & Arora, 2017).

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9693-1541

That is the main reason why organizations nowadays are called learning organizations which indicates continuous learning with the latest development (Saadat & Saadat, 2016). Competitive salary packages and benefits support employees' knowledge and skills. For example, the study of Francis and Kibera (2019) found correlations between organizational culture and work performance. Al-Omari and Okasheh (2017) investigated the influence of work environment on employees' performance and found that work environment had a major impact on the employees' work performance. In terms of Leadership, Khan, et.al (2020), studied the effect of the transformational leadership style and found that transformational leadership influences work performance. The same case with attitude and work values affects the employees' work performance (Liao, et.al, 2012).

There have been few studies related to organizational climate and performance. Thus, the current study enriched the discussion on such a field, fill the gap, and examine the effect of organizational climate on employees' work performance.

The study is divided into several parts. The first part explains the background and the purpose of the study. The second part is the literature review which presents the existing literature and studies that have discussed the current topic thus establishing the theoretical foundation of the study. The third part is the research methodology which presents the research design, locale, population, procedures, instruments, and the statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the presentation of data and analysis. This part presents the data that was gathered through research instruments and analyzed using statistical software. The fifth part is the result and discussion of its contribution to the existing knowledge.

Literature Review

The literature review intends to discuss the study. The purpose is to gain a deeper understanding of the topic and establish the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study. The presentation was arranged thematically and then followed by the conceptual framework.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Organizational Climate Concept and its Influence on Employees.

The current study defined organizational climate as an organizational environment that can influence employees' motivation, attitude, and behavior. Litwin and Stringer (1968) as cited in Ahuja and Narula (2016) likewise defined organizational climate as "a set of measurable properties of the work environment that is directly or indirectly perceived by the people who live and work in a particular environment and is assumed to influence their motivation and behavior". It is along the concept of Pritchard and Karasick (1973) as cited in Ahuja and Naula (2016) that organizational climate was defined as "a relatively enduring quality of an organization's internal environment wherein the behavior and policies of the members in the organization serve as bases for interpreting situations and act as sources for directing activity". Concerning organizational climate, Lock (1969) as cited in Maqbool, et.al. (2020) defined it as "a source of pleasant conditions at the workplace; it is a positive emotional state which can be measured from positive job experiences. The feeling of employees as a result of their assessment of the internal environment of

the organization produces a certain level of satisfaction toward their job (Veldman, et.al, 2013, cited by Maqbool, et.al, 2020).

Existing studies have provided results on the correlation between organizational climate and job satisfaction. For example, the study of Maqbool, et.al (2020) found that all variables measured namely role, clarity, respect, communication, reward system, career development, planning, decision making, innovation, relationships, teamwork, support, conflict management, commitment, morale, training, and learning and the direction of the company are correlated to the job satisfaction. In terms of organizational climate and employees' organizational commitment, Berberoglu (2018) presented a positive correlation between the two variables. Similarly, organizational climate correlates with work engagement.

Organizational climates such as clarity, standards, individual responsibility, flexibility, reward, recognition, and team commitment affect the work engagement of the employees (Abun, et.al. 2021, Chaudhary, et.al, 2013, Clement & Eketu, 2019). It is also true with individual work performance as pointed out in the study of Permarupan, et.al (2013). A positive work environment affects the employees' work behavior positively, reversely, it can influence counterproductive behavior (Lipińska-Grobelny, 2021). The more positive the work climate is, the more committed and happy employees become as pointed out by Batubara and El-Hami (2018).

Elements of Organizational Climate

Organizational climate has been defined as an internal environment of an organization that characterizes an organization resulting from the behavior and policies of an organization (Ahuja & Naula (2016). For example, Drigo Consulting Group (2003) identifies flexibility, responsibility, standards, rewards, clarity, and team commitment. While Davidson, et.al (2001) pointed out leader facilitation and support; professional and organizational esprit; conflict and ambiguity; regulations, organization, and pressure; job variety, challenge, and autonomy; job standards, workgroup cooperation, friendliness, and warmth. Balachandran and Thomas (2007) also named several dimensions of organizational climate namely welfare concern, norms and standards, interpersonal relations, recruitment and training, recognition and encouragement, job security, fair rewards, job autonomy, freedom and control, and red tape. Lone, et.al (2017), however, classified only two dimensions of organizational climate which are called human relation climate and rational goal climate.

This study adopted several dimensions: clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward, and team commitment. These elements must be present in an organization to create a positive organizational climate.

Clarity Climate

Gore (2017) defines clarity as clearness, lucidity, and freedom from ambiguity. He emphasized that this is one of the functions and competencies of leadership. Along with this concept, Hey Group (2003) defines clarity as the employees' understanding of the vision and mission and the contribution of the department and units to achieve the vision and mission. Abun, et.al (2021) indicated that ensuring clarity means that the management needs to put in place and makes

it clear to the employees about the strategic direction of the organization, ensuring the works of different units are aligned to accomplish the vision-mission or strategic direction.

Standards Climate

Abun, et.al. (2021) defined standards climate as a "benchmark provided by the organization that everyone has to follow in carrying out their duties and responsibilities". It is a gauge to measure the quality of their outputs and to measure the quality of their moral behavior (Abun, et.al, 2021). Cenelec (2013) contended that standards are used by organizations to ensure the quality and safety of products which leads to customer satisfaction.

According to Fernandez (2017), businesses need to establish sets of expectations to which everyone is held accountable. Abun, et.al. (2021) relatively mentioned that it is important for management to assign objectives that are defined and measurable. Beyond that, the management needs to define procedures and effective work behaviors. The ways how to achieve these objectives must be discussed with the employees.

Individual Responsibility Climate

Collins Dictionary defines responsibility as "assigned duties because of your job or position". This is in line with what Litwin and Stringer (1967) mean about individual responsibility. According to Litwin and Stringer (1967), employees must be given the freedom to decide, work and exercise their authority in their workplace.

Flexibility Climate

Madhani (2013) defined flexibility as "the main capability that enables organizations to face environmental fluctuations, as it makes them more responsive to change". While He et.al (2014) define organizational flexibility as "the ability to cope with environmental uncertainty which enables enterprises to survive and develop from organizational change and transformation". Rose (n.d) defines it as "adaptability, openness, and intensity at which an organism adapts to its changing environment". Based on these definitions, this study defined flexibility as the ability to adjust to new ways of doing things as required by the situation. This definition is related to Abun's, et.al (2021) study manifests that the reason for flexibility is the unstable external environment of the organization. Abun, et.al (2021) further defined flexibility as the ability to create, experiment, challenge the norms, reduce bureaucratic processes, introduce new ideas, and apply a win-win solution in problem-solving".

Reward and Recognition Climate

These two terms are often used interchangeably, and people use them to mean the same thing. In the business, the reward is defined as "the return for the performance of the desired behavior and positive reinforcement" (Aksakal & Dağdeviren, 2014). It is a strategy to motivate and reinforce good behavior. Thus, when the word reward and recognition are used together, a tangible reward for excellent performance and recognition in the form of acknowledgment or praise must be given to the individual who performs well. Correspondingly, Abun, et.al (2021) highlighted that employees must be rewarded monetarily or advancement, or non-monetary reward in form of recognition or praise.

Team Commitment

Organizational behavioral theorists use the difference between the two terms. Newstrom (2015) distinguishes the difference between the two words. A group means two or more people who interact with each other to accomplish a goal. According to Newstrom (2015), a group focuses on personal progress, not the team, decisions are not participative, and no one respects the quality of others. Forsyth, (2010) defined a team as "structured groups of people working based on well-defined common goals that require coordinated interactions to perform certain tasks". For the team to accomplish the goal, one must have the knowledge, skills, and specialized ability to contribute (Levi, 2001). As Preda (2006) stated, team members must have complementary skills that they use to carry out their tasks to accomplish the goal. The philosophy behind teamwork is that the intelligence of a group exceeds the intelligence of a person considering the right conditions are met (Wooly, et.al, 2015, cited by Luden, (2016).

Individual Work Performance as Multidimensional Construct

It is a reality that the concept of individual work performance seems to vary among different authors. For example, Patro (2019) defines work performance as "the accomplishment of the assigned task for achieving the organizational goal". Orta (2018) likewise defines work performance as "how well an employee is executing the expected related work activities". These two definitions were published in IGI Global (n.d) and used as the main concept in the conduct of performance appraisal of Pereira (2020). They refer to work performance in terms of outcome, productivity, and quality. Even Sauermann (2016) views individual work performance from the aspects of quality, quantity, work productivity, and workplace conduct. However, Campbell (1990) as cited in Jacobs, et.al (2013), is offering a different view of work performance. He explained that work performance or job performance is a means used to reach the established goal within a job or organization. Sonnetag and Frese (2001) gave an example of a performance outcome that is not related to work performance. Imagine a teacher who delivers excellent instruction, but several of the students failed the subject because they are slow learners. Another example is an excellent research professor who teaches research and produces lesser research-capable students due to other responsibilities. Considering these scenarios, the authors agree that when conceptualizing performance, one needs to differentiate between behavioral components and outcome components of performance (Campbell, 1990; Campbell, McCloy, Oppler, & Sager, 1993; Kanfer, 1990; Roe, 1999).

Several types of research on measuring individual work performance have been done, however, no common approach was identified for the dimensions to be measured (Koopmans, et.al. 2012). Varied approaches were used such as outcome, productivity, absenteeism, and presenteeism as the basis for measuring individual work performance (Koopmans, 2014). Campbell (1990) measures the behavior or action of individual work performance. Congruently, this study considered the concern of having no common conceptual framework for measuring individual work performance viewing it with a multidimensional construct. Thus, Campbell's (1990) concept related to measuring individual work performance was considered.

Measuring individual work performance is measuring the work behavior or individual actions that one uses to achieve a goal which involves a multidimensional construct (Campbell, 1990; Austin and Villanova, 1992). Measuring

individual work performance includes contextual performance and counterproductive behavior which were immediately reflected in the works of Rotundo and Sackett, (2002), and Viswesvaran and Ones, (2000). Other researchers such as Sonnentag and Frese (2001), Koopmans, et.al (2012), Koopmans (2014), Abun, et.al (2021), and Abun, et.al (2021) have measured individual work performance from three different dimensions namely task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior.

Task performance has been defined by researchers such as Bormann and Motowidlo (1993, 2009) as “the effectiveness with which job positions perform activities that contribute to the organization's technical core either directly, implementing a part of its technological process, or indirectly, providing it with needed materials or services”. This definition refers to task performance as job-specific task proficiency, technical proficiency, or in-role performance (Koopmans, et.al, 2012). Harrison, Newman, & Roth, (2006) as cited in Daryoush, et.al (2013) define task performance as "the ability to meet expectations and demonstrate competency and expertise". These two definitions are enough to emphasize that task performance pertains to the technical skills and competency of the person to carry out a task successfully. By possessing technical skills and knowledge, the person can fulfill his/her duties and responsibilities to a given task/job (Murphy & Shiarella, 1997). In short, task performance is behaviors that are oriented to the accomplishment of the task or job.

Relatively, Dođru (2019) defines contextual performance as “the degree to which an employee behaves positively consisting of volunteering for extra duties, helping coworkers, and cooperating with them with an expectation of a reward”. Additionally, Yedgarian (2021) defines it as “a measure of the effectiveness of an individual’s relationship with other employees, which goes beyond just doing a job and contributes to an organization’s effectiveness”. In other words, contextual performance is the positive behaviors that are carried out voluntarily beyond prescribed duties and responsibilities to help others and the organization. These behaviors include altruism, conscientiousness, civic virtue, courtesy, sportsmanship (Organ, 2015), demonstrating effort, facilitating team performance, cooperating, and communicating (Rotundo and Sackett, 2002; Campbell, 1990).

The third dimension of individual work performance is counterproductive behaviors which are harmful to the organization (Koopmans, 2014). Or Zhou (2020) defines it as "voluntary behaviors that harm the organization or people working in that organization" or "behaviors directed against other individuals or against the organization that employs the individual" (van Eerde, 2016). There are a lot of examples related to these behaviors such as absenteeism, being late at work, engaging in off-task behavior, theft, substance abuse (Koopmans, 2014), hazardous behavior leading to loss of productivity, or damage, work avoidance behavior, (Murphy, 2014) as cited in Sadeh and Baskin-Sommers, (2016), unruliness, theft, and drug misuse (Hunt, 1996), calling in sick when not ill, insulting another employee, and stealing something from the employer (Zhou, 2020), procrastination, using employers’ time for personal benefits (van Eerde, 2016).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Source: Hay Group (2003) and Drigo Consulting Group (2003), Sonnentag and Frese(2001), Koopmans, et.al (2012).

Figure 1: The conceptual framework describes the correlation between organizational climate and work performance. It explains the effect of an organization on the work performance of employees.

Statement of the Problems.

The study aims to measured the effect of organizational climate on the individual work performance of employees. It answered specifically the following questions:

1. What is the organizational climate of the institution in terms of;

- 1.1 clarity;
- 1.2 standards;
- 1.3 responsibility;
- 1.4 flexibility;
- 1.5 reward and recognition, and
- 1.6 team commitment?

2. What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:

- 2.1 task performance;
- 2.2 contextual performance, and
- 2.3 counterproductive behavior?

3. Is there a relationship between organizational climate and individual work performance?

Assumption

The study assumed that organizational climate affects the individual work performance of employees and it can be measured.

Hypothesis

The study of Abun, et.al (2021) found a correlation between organizational climate and work engagement. Thus, the current study hypothesizes that there is a correlation between organizational climate and the individual work performance of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limited its investigation to the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag and focused its discussion only on the six dimensions of organizational climate and three dimensions of individual work performance.

Research Methodology

As required by scientific research, it needs to follow a prescribed research methodology. It is the specific procedure to be followed in investigating. This is the basis for the determination of the quality and validity of the research (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003 as cited by Abun, et.al, 2021). Along with such a concept, this part presents the methodology of how this study was conducted. Subsequently, it followed the prescribed rules of investigating so that there is a research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of organizational climate and its effect on the work engagement of employees. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of The Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte.

Population

Those who answered the questionnaires are all employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag Ilocos Norte. Since the number of faculty and employees were limited, total enumeration was applied.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires of Hay Group Consulting (2003) on organizational climate and Koopmans, et.al (2012) on individual work performance.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the researcher distributed the questionnaires, letters were sent to the president of the college to request permission to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in their respective institutions. Upon the president's approval, the questionnaires were floated, collected, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data gathered. The weighted mean determined the level of organizational climate of the schools while the ANOVA measured the correlation between organizational climate and individual work performance of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Range Of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree/High
2.51 – 3.50	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree/Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data are presented through tables and followed by their interpretation. The tables are arranged according to the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the organizational climate of the institution in terms of;

- 1.1 clarity;
- 1.2 standards;
- 1.3 responsibility;
- 1.4 flexibility;
- 1.5 reward and recognition, and
- 1.6 team commitment?

Table 1: Organizational Climate in terms of Clarity.

No	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation (DI)
	Clarity		
1.	The strategic direction of the college, as well as the direction of the department and its functions, are clear	3.75	A/H
2.	The work of different levels in the college fits together to accomplish its mission	3.79	A/H
3.	Employees are involved in discussing the strategic direction and strategies on how to get there	3.72	A/H
4.	The employees understand the “whys” of the management’s decision related to employees’ well-being	3.64	A/H
5.	Policy guidelines are communicated to employees	3.70	A/H
6.	The lines of authority, as well as roles and responsibilities, are spelled out	3.68	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.71	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003)

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly agree/Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree/High
2.51 – 3.50	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree/Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly disagree/very low

The data revealed that the organizational climate concerning the issue of clarity obtained a composite mean rating of 3.71 which is interpreted as "agree" or high". This composite mean suggests that the organizational climate of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of clarity is high. Even when the indicators are taken singly, they are rated within the interpretation of “agree or high”, specifically, the direction of the institution, the direction of work toward the

accomplishment of the vision and mission, employee involvement in setting the direction of the institution, employees' understanding concerning the reasons behind management's decision related to their well-being, institution's policies are communicated and explained, and roles and authority are clearly defined.

Organizational clarity is a very important issue in an organization. According to Burton, et.al (2020), it is about employees' understanding of the organization's vision and mission, purpose, strategy, opportunities, challenges, priorities, and competitive reality. Burton further (2020) pointed out the significance of organizational clarity on organizational success. This was also supported by Ali's (2019) study about the effect of organizational clarity on team performance. It emphasized that when the team gets a clear picture of where the organization is heading and the tasks are clearly defined and leading toward the objectives, the team becomes motivated to perform. This is confirmed by Hansson and Anderzen (2009) in their study about the effect of organizational clarity on organizational well-being which discovered that work with goal clarity improves organizational well-being.

Table 2: Organizational climate in terms of standards

No	Indicator Standards	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Employees are given challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish	3.65	A/H
2	Employees are involved in determining and monitoring the objectives	3.72	A/H
3	The objectives to be achieved are measurable	3.69	A/H
4	Effective work behaviors to achieve the objectives are defined	3.60	A/H
5	There are prescribed procedures to be followed by employees in carrying out their jobs	3.72	A/H
6	Quality standards are clearly defined and understood by employees	3.69	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.68	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003).

The whole organizational climate in terms of standards gained a composite mean of 3.68 which means "agree or high". The organizational climate of Divine Word College of Laoag is also high. Even if the items are taken separately, all items under the "standards" dimension of organizational climate obtained the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of "agree or high", particularly along with the items of "challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish, employee participation in determining the objectives, measurable objectives, defined work behaviors to achieve the objective, prescribed procedures to be followed, and quality standards are defined".

Studies have been conducted concerning the effect of organizational performance. For example, the study by Neyestani and Juanzon (2017) established that organizational standards affect positively internal business processes. Satyendra (2017) presented a similar conclusion that organizational standards help improve products and services and enhance the performance level of the organization in terms of efficient and effective processes.

Table 3: Responsibility

No	Indicator Responsibility	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	There is a delegation of authority down to the lower level	3.66	A/H
2	Minimum number of interferences to ensure autonomy	3.70	A/H
3	Employees are encouraged to cooperate, communicate and practice teamwork on their own	3.71	A/H
4	Provide sufficient room for employees to take initiative and calculated risks	3.60	A/H
5	Holds employees accountable for their performance	3.72	A/H
6	Coaches and counsels employees to manage their problems-solving efforts	3.70	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.68	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003).

In terms of responsibility, this obtained a composite mean rating of 3.68 which is considered “agree or high”. This composite mean rating indicates that organizational climate related to responsibility is not very high and it is not also very low, low, or moderate but it is high. Even if the indicators are taken separately, all items are rated within the same level of mean rating with the same interpretation as “agree or high” like delegating authority to subordinates, giving autonomy to subordinates to perform their tasks, promoting cooperation and teamwork, encouraging risk-taking and initiative behavior, holding employees accountable for their performance, coaching, and counseling employees to manage their problem-solving efforts.

According to Blaga (2014), individual responsibility in the workplace is an organizational culture that is based on three principles: reliability, transparency, and autonomy. These three principles imply that there is trust and open communication between management and subordinates. The management trusts their employees that they can do their tasks and accomplish their objectives without being monitored or supervised closely. Satyendra (2018) explained that management expects employees to be responsible for their job and the objectives assigned to them. Giving them the authority to carry out their duties and responsibilities is essential. Al-Jammal, et al. (2015) agreeably stated that delegating authority to employees to decide what to do with their tasks results in efficiency, effectiveness, and empowerment. Suárez-Albanchez’s, et al. (2022) study reiterated the positive effect of autonomy on the employees' psychological well-being and work commitment.

Table 4: Flexibility

	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Flexibility		
1	Encourages creativity, experimentation, and independent thinking	3.68	A/H
2	People are not afraid of challenging the norms	3.66	A/H
3	Less bureaucratic steps in the work process	3.66	A/H
4	Be willing to accept other viewpoints that are useful	3.65	A/H
5	Encourages new ideas into practice	3.68	A/H
6	Works for “win-win” rather than “win-lose” solutions	3.71	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.67	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003)

The flexibility of employees gained a composite mean rating of 3.67 described as "agree or high". It means that the organizational climate along with flexibility is high. Even when the indicators are taken singly, all items are rated within the same range mean rating level with the same interpretation as “agree/high” such as encouraging creativity, experimentation, independent thinking, not being afraid of challenging the norms, being less bureaucratic in the work process, being open to new ideas, encouraging new ideas into practice and applying the win-win solution to problems.

Smith, et al. (2019) pointed out that firms must have policies that support flexibility and such an environment can attract, retain, and satisfy human resource capital. Studies have been conducted concerning the effect of work flexibility on work performance. For example, Coenen and Kok (2014) discovered that work flexibility affects team performance, product development, and employee work engagement (Weideman & Hofmeyr, 2020).

Table 5: Rewards and Recognition

	Indicator	Weighted mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Rewards and Recognition		
1.	Provides detailed performance standards to both individual employees and teams/departments	3.70	A/H
2.	Employees are rewarded on time and performance-based	3.62	A/H
3.	Advancement opportunities are provided for talented employees	3.56	A/H
4.	There are non-monetary ways of rewarding individual and group performance	3.54	A/H
5.	There are opportunities for promotion for those who perform	3.58	A/H
6.	Management is humble enough to express expressing their positive feedback to employees who accomplish their job well	3.58	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.60	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003).

The composite mean rating of 3.60 which is considered as “agree or high” suggests that the organizational climate related to rewards and recognition is high. Taking the indicators separately, the employees agree that the institution provides performance standards for the individual or department and rewards for good performance, promotes talented employees, and gives feedback to the employees who have accomplished their tasks.

Rewards and recognition have been recognized as important tools to motivate employees and improve performance. Hansen, et al (2016) argued that rewards and recognition should be treated distinctively and only then it motivates the employees and enhance performance. Amoatema and Kyeremeh (2016) emphasized that management should provide resources to implement employees' reward and recognition programs. Studies have found rewards and recognition significantly correlate with work performance work (Ali & Ahmad, 2008, Janakbhai & Pathak, 2021, Baskar, 2013, Danish & Usman, 2010, Bowen, et al., 2020, Mesep, 2016, Hansen, et al., 2002, Neining, et al., 2010).

Table 6: Team Commitment

	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Team Commitment		
No			
1	My team has a great deal of personal meaning to me.	3.73	A/H
2	I have to work in a team out of	3.80	A/H
3	I feel I am making an effort not only for myself but also for my team.	3.70	A/H
4	I feel a sense of belonging to my team.	3.69	A/H
5	I feel the cooperative spirit of my team and not competition.	3.76	A/H
6	I always consider the input of others when making-decision	3.73	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.69	A/H

Source: Hay Group (2003).

The employees' team commitment obtained a composite mean rating of 3.69 which is understood as "agree or high". Even if the indicators are taken singly, all of them are rated within the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of "agree or high". Employees agree that there is a team that gives meaning to them, they work not only for themselves but also for the team, and they feel that they are belonged to the team and participate in decision-making.

Team commitment has been a contributing factor to organizational performance as suggested by several studies. Neining, et al. (2010) confirmed this when they mentioned that team commitment plays a vital role in job satisfaction, intention to stay, work commitment, performance, and altruism. Similarly, Aube, et al (2014) support this

when they emphasized that team goal commitment improves team performance. Their study confirmed Neiningger, 's et al. (2010) study about the positive effect of team commitment on work commitment and work performance.

Problem 2: What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:

- 2.1 task performance;
- 2.2 contextual performance, and
- 2.3 counterproductive behavior?

Table 7: Task Performance

	Indicator	Weighted mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Task Performance		
1.	I manage to plan my work so that it was done on time	3.86	A/H
2.	My planning was optimal	3.86	A/H
3.	I kept in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work	3.83	A/H
4.	I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work	3.78	A/H
5.	I knew how to set the right priorities	3.84	A/H
6.	I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort	3.86	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.86	A/H

Source: Koopmans, et al (2012).

The individual work performance of employees concerning task performance gained a composite mean rating of 3.86 which is considered as "agree or high". Even when the indicators are taken separately, all the items are rated within the same level of mean rating with the interpretation of "agree or high". All employees agree to a certain extent that they manage to finish their work as planned, optimally plan their work, and achieve the results, know how to set priorities, achieve the result with minimal time, and can separate issues from side issues at work.

Task performance is viewed as a core job responsibility of an employee. It is job-specific behaviors that are reflected in their job description (Koopmans, et al. 2011), such as functions of knowledge, skills, and abilities. Gao, et al. (2021) stated that employees who have high task performance capability tend to be more self-controlled, more responsible, and more persistent in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. As a result, they focus more on their task and achieve high-performance ratings. Whiting, et al. (2008) conform to this when they indicated that high task performance, such as conscientiousness, affects performance evaluation.

Table 8: Contextual Performance

	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Contextual Performance		
1.	I took on extra responsibilities	3.80	A/H
2.	I started a new task myself when my old ones were finished	3.76	A/H
3.	I took on a challenging work task, when available	3.74	A/H
4.	I worked at keeping my job knowledge up to date	3.71	A/H
5.	I worked at keeping my job skills up to date	3.74	A/H
6.	I came up with creative solutions to new problems	3.76	A/H
7.	I kept looking for new challenges in my job	3.76	A/H
8.	I did more than was expected of me	3.76	A/H
9.	I actively participated in work meetings	3.72	A/H
10.	I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work	3.71	A/H
11.	I grasped opportunities when they presented themselves	3.70	A/H
12.	I knew how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly	3.76	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.74	A/H

Source: Source: Koopmans, et al (2012).

The individual work performance of employees along with the contextual performance gained a composite mean rating of 3.74 which is considered as "agree or high". Taking it singly, all indicators are rated within the same level of mean rating with the same interpretation of "agree or high". Employees agree to a certain extent that they took extra responsibilities, started new tasks when the old ones finished, took a challenging task when available, kept themselves up to date with the latest knowledge and skills, came up with creative solutions to problems encountered in the workplace, did more than expected, participated in the work meetings, looked for ways to improve performance and solving difficult situations quickly.

Contextual performance is viewed as discretionary behaviors that are not prescribed. Moreover, these are performed voluntarily (Borman & Motowidlow, 1993; Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994). They are attributes related to personality and motivation. The behaviors are needed for the overall well-being of the organization. Remarkably, several studies with similar results have been conducted concerning the positive effect of contextual performance on employees' effectiveness (Griffin, et al, 2001), and organizational effectiveness (Borman et al., 1995; Dunlop & Lee, 2004).

Table 9: Counterproductive Work Behavior

	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
No	Counterproductive Work Behavior		
1.	I complained about unimportant matters at work	3.21	SWA/M
2.	I made problems greater than they were at work	3.16	SWA/M
3.	I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects	3.06	SWA/M
4.	I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work	3.06	SWA/M
5.	I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work	3.05	SWA/M
6.	I did less than was expected of me	3.09	SWA/M
7.	I managed to get off from a work task easily	3.10	SWA/M
8.	I sometimes did nothing when I should have been working	3.08	SWA/M
	Composite Mean	3.10	SWA/M

Source: Source: Koopmans, et al (2012).

The composite mean rating of 3.10 indicates that individual work performance concerning counterproductive work behavior is moderate. Employees agree to a moderate extent that they complained about unimportant matters, made problems greater than they were at work, focused on the negative aspects of work situation, spoke with colleagues and other people from outside about the negative aspects of their work, did less than what was expected of them, got out of work easily and sometimes did nothing while they should have been working.

Shen and Lei (2022) contended that counterproductive work behavior is detrimental to an organization and its stakeholders as it affects economic efficiency and work relationship in the organization. Consequently, the need for management to reduce negative work behaviors (Sypniewska, 2020) would make a massive difference in employee performance and work engagement (Bagyo, 2018).

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between organizational climate and individual work performance?

a. Organizational Climate and Task Performance

The organizational climate factors of clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment taken together significantly predicted the employees' task performance $F(6,160) = 18.062, p < .01$ with

.644 overlap between the predictor variables (e.g., clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment) and employees' task performance.

Specifically, flexibility $B = .523$ $p < .01$, rewards and recognition $B = -.370$ $p < .01$, and team commitment $B = .667$ $p < .01$, 1.178 quantified the regression equation.

Hence, organizational factors such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment could predict individual employees' task performance. However, when the organizational factors were taken singly, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment could predict the employees' task performance.

Table 10: Model Summary (Organizational Climate and Task Performance)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.644 ^a	.415	.392	.38650

a. Predictors: (Constant), TEAM COMMITMENT, RESPONSIBILITY, REWARD & RECOGNITION, FLEXIBILITY, CLARITY, STANDARDS

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.189	6	2.698	18.062	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.855	153	.149		
	Total	39.044	159			

a. Dependent Variable: TASK PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), TEAM COMMITMENT, RESPONSIBILITY, REWARD & RECOGNITION, FLEXIBILITY, CLARITY, STANDARDS

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.178	.313		3.768	.000
	CLARITY	-.126	.118	-.130	-1.068	.287
	STANDARDS	-.050	.128	-.055	-.394	.694
	RESPONSIBILITY	.066	.134	.066	.490	.625
	FLEXIBILITY	.523	.109	.516	4.801	.000
	REWARDS & RECOGNITION	-.370	.094	-.408	-3.946	.000
	TEAM COMMITMENT	.667	.101	.540	6.576	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TASK PERFORMANCE

b. Organizational Climate and Contextual Performance

When the organizational climate factors of clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment are taken together they could significantly predict the employees’ contextual performance $F(6,160) = 24.472, p < .01$ with .720 overlap between the organizational climate factors and contextual performance.

In particular, clarity $B = -.199, p < .05$, responsibility $B = .398, p < .01$, flexibility $B = .295, p < .01$, rewards and recognition $B = -.254, p < .01$, and team commitment $B = .647, p < .01$, .817 quantified the regression equation.

Therefore, organizational factors such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment could significantly predict the employees' contextual performance. However, when the organizational factors are taken separately it was only the organizational climates of clarity, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment that could predict the employees' performance.

Table 11: Model Summary (Organizational Climate and Contextual Performance).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.720 ^a	.519	.500	.30672

a. Predictors: (Constant), TEAM COMMITMENT, RESPONSIBILITY, REWARD & RECOGNITION, FLEXIBILITY, CLARITY, STANDARDS

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	15.507	6	2.584	27.472	.000 ^b
Residual	14.393	153	.094		
Total	29.900	159			

a. Dependent Variable: CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), TEAM COMMITMENT, RESPONSIBILITY, REWARD & RECOGNITION, FLEXIBILITY, CLARITY, STANDARDS

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.817	.248		3.295	.001
1 CLARITY	-.199	.094	-.234	-2.123	.035
STANDARDS	-.104	.101	-.129	-1.022	.308
RESPONSIBILITY	.398	.107	.457	3.735	.000
FLEXIBILITY	.295	.086	.332	3.411	.001
REWARD & RECOGNITION	-.254	.074	-.320	-3.406	.001
TEAM COMMITMENT	.647	.080	.599	8.041	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE

c. Organizational Climate and Counterproductive Behavior

The different organizational climate factors of clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment when taken as a group could significantly predict the employees' counterproductive behavior, $F(6, 160) = 3.738$ $p < .01$ with .358 overlap between the predictor variables (e.g., clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, and team commitment) and the employees' counterproductive behavior.

However, when the organizational climate factors were taken singly, none of them could significantly predict the employees' counterproductive behavior.

Table 12: Model Summary (Organizational Climate and Counterproductive Behavior)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error in the Estimate
1	.358 ^a	.128	.094	.85959

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.571	6	2.762	3.738	.002 ^b
	Residual	113.050	153	.739		
	Total	129.621	159			

a. Dependent Variable: COUNTERPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

b. Predictors: (Constant), TEAM COMMITMENT, RESPONSIBILITY, REWARD & RECOGNITION, FLEXIBILITY, CLARITY, STANDARDS

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.725	.695		1.043	.298
	CLARITY	.473	.263	.266	1.797	.074
	STANDARDS	-.360	.284	-.215	-1.268	.207
	RESPONSIBILITY	-.130	.299	-.072	-.437	.663
	FLEXIBILITY	.128	.242	.070	.530	.597
	REWARD & RECOGNITION	.387	.209	.234	1.855	.065
	TEAM COMMITMENT	.150	.225	.067	.667	.506

a. Dependent Variable: COUNTERPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

Results and Discussions

The study explored the effects of organizational climate on the individual work performance of employees. Organizational climate significantly affects the individual work performance of employees. This connotes management's development priorities must zero in on issues concerning clarity, organizational standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment. Leadership Framework Network (2022) contends that one of the manager's roles is to set the right condition for productive work. For example, people perform their work when they are clear about their goals, know what is expected of them, and know the boundaries within

which they must work, given some freedom to determine how they are going to achieve their goals, and have clear and shared understanding of the work to be performed.

Ensuring clarity on the task to be performed and how to work with others is vital. Subsequently, there must be standards measurement for the accomplishment of the objectives and behaviors (Satyendra, 2017). Given those standards, the assurance of getting things done is not guaranteed. Hence, it must be accompanied by employees' responsibility as Sibert, et al. (2011) mentioned: "giving employees responsibility is one way of inviting them to participate in managing the organization." Their study further points out that greater involvement increases employees' responsibility and becomes more involved in organizational strategy. Hence, there is increased commitment, job satisfaction, task, and contextual performance.

Responsibility in this context means empowerment which implies flexibility. Center for Creative Leadership (2022) asserts that organizations, nowadays, need to embrace flexibility amid the pandemic. Employees and management need to embrace uncertainty and flexibility because it not only boosts well-being but also builds on employee productivity (Castrillon, 2022) and performance (Prasad & Mishra, 2021). Consequently, reward and recognition become important elements of organizational management. There are many studies suggesting their essence in improving motivation (Baskar, 2013, Baskar & Rajkumar, 2013, Abebau, 2020), performance Manzoor, et al. (2021), Patel (2015). Moreover, fostering team commitment is fundamental as several studies show its inclusion into one of the management priorities to increase employees' performance (Dordevic, et al (2020).

Given the result of the study, this paves the way to understanding the work environment as an important management priority. An unfavorable organizational climate may hinder the productive performance of the organization (Ashkanasy & Härtel, 2014, Aarons, & Sawitzky, 2006). It also affects the employee's commitment (Permarupan, et al. 2013), counterproductive behavior (Kanten & Er Ülker, 2013), and negative commitment (El Kassar, et al. 2011).

Conclusion

The organizational climate of Divine Word College of Laoag is considered high along with clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, recognition, and team commitment. Similarly, individual work performance is high, except for counterproductive work behavior, which is rated moderate. Concerning the correlation between organizational climate and individual work performance, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) found a significant correlation between organizational climate and individual work performance. The findings suggest that refining organizational climate affects individual work performance positively.

The study contributes to the current debate on the effect of organizational climate on organizational and individual performance. However, there is a need to conduct another study concerning the effect of organizational climate on the organizational citizenship behavior of employees with a wider coverage and a larger number of respondents.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, D.A. M.T.N. Methodology, D.A., M.T.N. **Data Collection:** D.A., M.T. **Formal analysis:** D.A., M.T.N. **Writing—original draft preparation:** D.A., M.T.N. **Writing—review and editing:** D.A., M.T.N.

All authors have read and agreed to the published final version of the manuscript.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, and the research does not deal with vulnerable groups or sensitive issues.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding: The study is funded partially by the school and the authors

References

- Aarons, G. A., & Sawitzky, A. C. (2006). *Organizational climate partially mediates the effect of culture on work attitudes and staff turnover in mental health services*. Administration and policy in mental health, 33(3), 289–301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-006-0039-1>
- Abebaw, G. (2020). *Effects of rewards on employee motivation*. Munich: GRIN Verlag, <https://www.grin.com/document/946298>
- Abubakar, A.M., Elrehail, H., Alatailat, M.A. & Elci, A. (2019). *Knowledge Management, Decision-Making Style and Organizational Performance*. Journal of Innovation & Knowledge, 4(2), 104-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2017.07.003>
- Abun, D., Menor, R.I., Catbagan, N.C. Magallanes, T. & Ranay, F.B. (2021). *Organizational climate and work engagement of employees of divine word colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines*. International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science, 10(1), 107-121. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i1.1017>
- Abun, D., Nicolas, M.T., Apollo, E.P., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. (2021). *Employees' self-efficacy and work performance of employees as mediated by the work environment*. International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science, 10(7), 01-15. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i7.1470>
- Abun, D., Ubasa, A.L.A., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J., Ranay, F.B. (2021). *Attitude toward the work and its influence on the Individual work performance of employees: Basis for Attitude Management*. Technium Social Science Journal, 18, 378-394.
- Ahuja, J. & Narula, V. (2016). *A Demographic study on Organizational Climate: Indian vs. Multinational IT companies*. Pacific Business Review, 8(8).

- Aksakal, E. & Dağdeviren, M. (2014). *Analyzing Reward Management Framework with Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Methods*. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 147, 147-152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.131>
- Al-Jammal, H.R., Al-Khasawneh, A.L. Hasan, M. & Hammadat, M. (2015). *The Impact of the Delegation of Authority on Employees' Performance at Great Irbid Municipality: Case Study*. *International Journal of Human Resources Studies*, 5(3), 48-69. <https://doi.org/0.5296/ijhrs.v5i3.8062>.
- Ali, W. (2019). *Impact of Vision and Role Clarity on Team Performance*. Munich: GRIN Verlag. Retrieved from <https://www.grin.com/document/933144>
- Ali, R. & Ahmad, M.S. (2008). *The Impact of Reward and Recognition Programs on Employee's Motivation and Satisfaction: A Co Relational Study*. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5(4), 270-279.
- Al-Omari, K. & Okasheh, H. (2017). *The Influence of Work Environment on Job Performance: A Case Study of Engineering Company in Jordan*. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 12(24), 15544-15550.
- Amoatema, A.S. & Kyeremeh, D.D. (2016). *Making Employee Recognition a Tool for Achieving Improved Performance: Implication for Ghanaian Universities*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(34).
- Ariola, M.M. (2006). *Principles and Methods of Research*. Manila: National Bookstore
- Ashkanasy, N. M., & Härtel, C. E. J. (2014). *Positive and negative affective climate and culture: The good, the bad, and the ugly*. In B. Schneider & K. M. Barbera (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of organizational climate and culture* (pp. 136–152). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Aubé, C; Brunelle, É.; & Rousseau, V. (2014). *Flow Experience and Team Performance: The Role of Team Goal Commitment and Information Exchange, Motivation and Emotion*. New York: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-013-9365-2>
- Austin, J.T. and Villanova, P. (1992). *The criterion problem: 1917-1992*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 77(6), 836-74. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.77.6.836>
- Bagyo, Y. (2028). *The Effect of Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) And Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) on Employee Performance with Employee Engagement as an Intervening Variable*. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2002048389>
- Balachandran, M. & Thomas, I. (2007). *Dimensions of Organizational Climate*. *The Psychespace*, 1(1), 27-36.
- Baskar, P. (2013). *A Study on the Impact of Rewards and Recognition on Employee Motivation*. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(11), 1644. <https://doi.org/10.21275/v4i11.NOV151549>
- Basker, P. & Rajkumar, P. (2013). *A Study on the Impact of Rewards and Recognition on Employee Motivation*. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(11). <https://doi.org/10.21275/v4i11.NOV151549>

- Batubara, M. & El Hami, A. (2018). *Does Organizational Climate Effect on Employee Happiness Among Lecturers in Indonesia?* 10th International Conference on Language, Humanities, Education and Social Sciences, 18. <https://doi.org/10.15242/DiRPUB.DIRH0118039>
- Bennett, J.B. (2010). *Social Climate Research*. Wiley Online Library. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com>. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0885>.
- Blaga, A. (2014). *Individual Responsibility at the Workplace Means Performance for the Organization*. The KPI Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.performancemagazine.org>.
- Bormann, W.C. & Motowidlo, S.J. (2009). *Task Performance and Contextual Performance: The Meaning for Personnel Selection Research*. *Human Performance*, 10(2). https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327043hup1002_3
- Borman, W. C., & Motowidlo, S. J. (1993). *Expanding the criterion domain to include elements of contextual performance, Personnel selection in organizations*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 71-98.
- Borman, W. C., White, L. A., & Dorsey, D. W. (1995). *Effects of rate task performance and interpersonal factors on supervisor and peer performance ratings*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80(1), 168–177. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.80.1.168>
- Bowen, H. J., Marchesi, M. L., & Kensinger, E. A. (2020). *Reward motivation influences response bias on a recognition memory task*. *Cognition*, 203, 104337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2020.104337>
- Burton, K., Grates, G., Berger, B., Debreceeny, P., Kochhhar, S., & McCorkindale, T. (2020). *Organizational Clarity: The Case of Workforce Alignment & Belief*. Alabama: IPR (Institute for Public Relations).
- Campbell, J. (1990). *Modeling the performance prediction problem in industrial and organizational psychology*. In M. Dunnette & L. Hough (Eds.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 686–707). Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Campbell, J. P., McCloy, R. A., Oppler, S. H., & Sager, C. E. (1993). *A theory of performance*. In E. Schmitt, W. C. Borman, & Associates (Eds.), *Personnel selection in organizations* (pp. 35–70). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Castrilon, C. (2022). *Why Flexible Work Boosts Employee Productivity*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com>
- Cen- Cenelec (2013). *Standards and Your Business*. Retrieved from <https://www.cencenelec.eu>
- Center for Creative Leadership (CCL) (2022). *Flexible Work Benefits Organization*. Retrieved from <https://www.ccl.org>
- Chaudhary, R., Rangnekar, S. & Barua, M.K. (2013). *Organizational climate, climate strength, and work engagement*. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 133, 291 – 303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.195>

- Clement, O.I. & Eketu, C.A. (2019). *Organizational Climate and Employee Engagement in Banks in Rivers State, Nigeria*. International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Sciences, Technology, and Technology, 5(3).
- Coenen, M. & Kok, R.A.W. (2014). *Workplace flexibility and new product development performance: The role of telework and flexible work schedules*. European Management Journal, 32(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2013.12.003>.
- Danish, R. & Usman, A. (2010). *Impact of Reward and Recognition on Job Satisfaction and Motivation: An Empirical study from Pakistan*. International Journal of Business and Management, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v5n2p159>
- Daryoush, Y., Silong, A.D., Omar, Z. & Othman, J. (2013). *Improving Job Performance: Workplace Learning is the First Step*. International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.1n.1p.100>
- Davidson, M., Manning, M., Timo, N., & Ryder, P. (2001). *The Dimensions of Organizational Climate in Four- and Five-Star Australian Hotels*. Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research, 25(4), 444–461. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109634800102500406>
- Doğru, C. (2019). *The Effects of Perceived Organizational Support and Leader-Member Exchange on Contextual Performance: A Study in the Banking Sector*. In Handbook of Research on Contemporary Approaches in Management and Organizational Strategy. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge.
- Dordevic, B., Ivanovic-Dukic, M., Lopejevic, V. & Milanovic, S.S. (2020). *The impact of employees' commitment on organizational performances*. Strategic Management, 25(3), 25-37. <https://doi.org/10.5937/StraMan2003028D>
- Drigo Consulting Group (2003). *Creating a Performance Enhancing Organizational Climate*. Retrieved from <https://www.drigoconsultinggroup.com>
- Dunlop, P.D. & Lee, K. (2003). *Workplace deviance, organizational citizenship behavior, and business unit performance: the bad apples do spoil the whole barrel*. Journal of Organizational Behavior, 25(1), 67-80. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.243>
- Du Plessis, M. (2007). *The role of knowledge management in innovation*. Journal of Knowledge Management, 11 (4), 20-29.
- El- Kassar, A.N., Chams, N. & Karkouljian, S. (2011). *Organizational Climate and its Effects on the Employees' Commitment*. The Business Review, Cambridge, 19(1).
- Fernandez, J. (2017). *Without Management Standards Your Company Doesn't Know What It is Doing*. Entrepreneur: Asia Pacific. Retrieved from <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/286077>
- Forsyth, D.R. (2010). *Group dynamics, 5th edition*. Wadsworth: Cengage Learning, Belmont
- Gao, X., Chen, H., Wu, J. & Huang, J. (2021). *Task Performance: Report on the Study of Social and Emotional Skills of Chinese Adolescents*. Shanghai: Insights Publisher.

- Gore, G.W. (2017). *Organizational Clarity*. Team Trek Coaching Group. Retrieved from <https://www.teamtrek.com>
- Griffin, M., Neal, A. & Neale, M. (2001). *The Contribution of Task Performance and Contextual Performance to Effectiveness: Investigating the Role of Situational Constraints*. *Applied Psychology*, 49(3), 517-533. <https://www.doi.org/10.1111/1464-0597.00029>
- Hansen, F., Smith, M., & Hansen, R. B. (2002). *Rewards and Recognition in Employee Motivation*. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 34(5), 64-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886368702034005010>
- Hansen, F., Smith, M. & Hansen, R.B. (2002). *Compensation & Benefits Review*. London: Sage Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886368702034005010>
- Hansson, A. S., & Anderzén, I. (2009). *Goal clarity as an instrument for improved organizational well-being in the Church of Sweden*. *Work (Reading, Mass.)*, 33(1), 53–58. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-2009-0843>
- Harrison, D.A., Newman, D.A., & Roth, P.L. (2006). *How Important Are Job Attitudes? Meta-Analytic Comparisons of Integrative Behavioral Outcomes and Time Sequences*. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 49(2):305-325. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2006.20786077>
- Hay Group (2003). *Organizational Climate*. London: Hay Acquisition Company, Inc
- He, H., Baruch Y., & Lin C.P. (2014). *Modeling team knowledge sharing and team flexibility: the role of within-team competition*. *Human Relations*, 67(8):947–978. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726713508797>.
- Hunt, S. (1996). *Generic Work Behavior: An Investigation into the Dimensions of Entry-Level, Hourly Job Performance*. *Personnel Psychology*, 49(1), 51-83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1996.tb01791.x>
- IGI Global (n.d). *What is Performance Appraisal?* IGI Global: Publisher of Timely Knowledge. Retrieved from <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/approaches-and-methods-for-individual-performance-assessment-in-information-systems-projects/58873>.
- Jacobs K., Hellman M., Wuest E., Markowitz J. (2013) *Job Performance*. In: Gellman M.D., Turner J.R. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Behavioral Medicine*. New York: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1005-9_900
- Janakbhai, P.D. & Pathak, A. (2021). *A study on the impact of reward and recognition system on employee job satisfaction*. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 9(5).
- Joseph, O. O., & Kibera, F. (2019). *Organizational Culture and Performance: Evidence from Microfinance Institutions in Kenya*. *SAGE Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019835934>
- Kanfer, R. (1990). *Motivation Theory and Industry/Organizational Theory*. In M.D. Dunnette and L. Haugh (Eds). *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Paulo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologist Press.

Kanten, P. & Er Ülker, F. (2013). *The Effect of Organizational Climate on Counterproductive Behaviors: An Empirical Study on the Employees of Manufacturing Enterprises*. The Macrotheme Review 2(4).

Khan, H., Rehmat, M., & Butt, T.H. (2020). *Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout, and social loafing: a mediation model*. Future Business Journal 6, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-020-00043-8>

Koopmans, L., Bernaards, c., Hildebrandt, V., & van Buuren, S. (2012). *Development of an individual work performance questionnaire*. International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management, 62(1), 6 – 28. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17410401311285273>

Koopmans, L. (2014). *Measuring Individual Work Performance*. Leiden, Netherlands: CPI Koninklijke Wöhrmann, Zutphen.

Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C.M., Hildebrandt, V.H., Schaufeli, W.B., de vet H.C.W. & van der Beek, A.J. (2011). *Conceptual frameworks of individual work performance: A systematic review*. Journal of Occupational & Environmental Medicine, 53(8). <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0b013e318226a763>

Leadership Framework Network (2022). *How to Improve Clarity in the Workplace*. Retrieved from <https://assets.cdn.thewebconsole.com/S3WEB5366/images/How-to-improve-clarity-in-the-workplace.pdf>

Levi, D. (2001). *Groups Dynamics for Teams*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.

Lipińska-Grobelny, A. (2021). *Organizational climate and counterproductive work behaviors - the moderating role of gender*. Int J Occup Med Environ Health, 34(4):513-525. <https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.01623>. Epub 2021 Feb 19. PMID: 33630826.

Liao, C.W., Yu Lu, C., Huang, C.K. & Chiang, T.L. (2012). *Work values, work attitude, and job performance of green energy industry employees in Taiwan*. African Journal of Business Management 6(15) <https://doi.org/0.5897/AJBM11.1449>

Litwin, G. H. & Stringer, R.A. (1967). *Motivation and Organizational Climate*. Boston: Harvard University Press

Locke, E. A. (1969). *What is job satisfaction?* Organizational behavior and human performance, 4(4), 309-336. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(69\)90013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(69)90013-0)

Lone, J.A., Garnås, A., Myklebust, T., Bjørklund, R., Hoff, T., & Bjørkli, C. (2017). *Organizational climate and investigation performance in the Norwegian police: A qualitative study*. Journal of Investigative Psychology and Offender Profiling, 14(3), 227-245. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jip.1474>

Luden, D. (2016). *Are Two Heads Better than One?* Psychology Today. Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com>

Madhani, P. M., (2013). *Organizational Flexibility: Real Options Approach*. SCMS Journal of Indian Management, 10(3) 43-54.

Manzoor F, Wei L and Asif M (2021). *Intrinsic Rewards and Employee's Performance with the Mediating Mechanism of Employee's Motivation*. Frontier in Psychology, 12, 563070. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.563070>

Maqbool, S., Ismail, S.A.M.M. & Maqbool, S. (2020). *Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction in 21st Century Higher Educational Institutes*. Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews, 8(4), 577-586. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2020.8457>

McCombes, Sh. (2020). *Descriptive Research*. Scribbr. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com>

Mesepy, S.S. (2016). *The Impact of Reward and Recognition on Employee Engagement at PT. Bank Sulutgo, Manado*. Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi, 16(1).

Motowidlo, S.J. & Van Scotter, J.R. (1994). *Evidence that task performance should be distinct from contextual performance*. Journal of Applied Psychology, 79, (4), 475-480. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.79.4.475>

Murphy, K. R., & Shiarella, A. H. (1997). *Implications of the multidimensional nature of job performance for the validity of selection tests: Multivariate frameworks for studying test validity*. Personnel Psychology, 50(4), 823-854. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1997.tb01484.x>

Murphy, C. M., Stojek, M. K., MacKillop, J. (2014). *Interrelationships among impulsive personality traits, food addiction, and body mass index*. Appetite, 73, 45-50. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2013.10.008

Neininger, A., Lehmann-Willenbrock, N., Kauffeld, S. & Henschel, A. (2010). *Effects of a team and organizational commitment – A longitudinal study*. Journal of Vocational Behavior, 76(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2010.01.009>

Neyestani, B. & Juanzon, B.P. (2017). *ISO 9001 Standards and Organization's Performance: A Literature Review*. International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research, 4(2), 4-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22192/ijamr.2017.04.02.002>

Newstrom, J.W. (2015). *Organizational Behavior*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.

Nielsen, S.N. & Tieze, E. (2020). *Ecosystems Have Thermodynamic Openness*. In A New Ecology (Second Edition). Amsterdam: Elsevier Science.

Organ, D.W. (2015). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior*. In International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition). Amsterdam: Elsevier.

Orta, I.M. (2008). *Exploring Emotional Intelligence at Work: A Review of Current Evidence*. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge

Qiang, S. & Arora, A. (2017). *Worker Skill Estimation from Crowdsourced Mutual Assessments*. Journal of Organizational Psychology, 17(4).

- Patel, V. (2015). *Impact of reward and recognition on employee's performance*. International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Filed, 1(1).
- Patro, C.S. (2019). *Performance Appraisal*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global: Publisher of Timely Knowledge.
- Permarupan, P.Y., Saufi, R.A., Kasimc, S.R. & Balakrishnan, B.K. (2013). *The Impact of Organizational Climate on Employee's Work Passion and Organizational Commitment*. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 107, 88 – 95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.403>
- Pereira, J.L. (2020). *Approaches and Methods for Individual Performance Assessment in Information Systems Projects*. In Handbook of Research on the Role of Human Factors in IT Project Management. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge.
- Prasad, L. & Mishra, P. (2021). *Impact of work-life flexibility on work performance of the employees of IT Companies*. Psychology and Education Journal, 58(2). <https://doi.org/10.17762/pae.v58i2.3084>
- Preda, M. (2006). *Comportment organizational*. Romania: Polirom
- Pritchard, R. D., & Karasick, B. W. (1973). *The effects of organizational climate on managerial job performance and job satisfaction*. Organizational Behavior & Human Performance, 9(1), 126–146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(73\)90042-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(73)90042-1)
- Roe, R. A. (1999). *Work performance: A multiple regulation perspective*. In C. L. Cooper & I. T. Robertson (Eds.), International review of industrial and organizational psychology (14, 231–335). Chichester: Wiley.
- Rose, Sh. (n.d). *Organizational Flexibility*. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org>
- Rotundo, M. and Sackett, P.R. (2002). *The relative importance of the task, citizenship, and counterproductive performance to global ratings of performance: a policy-capturing approach*. Journal of Applied Psychology, 87(1), 66-80. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.87.1.66>
- Saadat, V. & Saadat, Z. (2016). *Organizational Learning as a Key Role of Organizational Success*. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, 230, 219-225. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.09.028>
- Sadeh, N. & Baskin-Sommers, A. (2016). *Risky, Impulsive, and Self-Destructive Behavior Questionnaire (RISQ): A Validation Study*. Assessment, 24(8), 1080–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073191116640356>
- Satyendra (2017). *Standards and Their Importance for Organizational Performance*. Ispat Guru. Retrieved from <https://www.ispatguru.com>.
- Sauermann, J. (2016) *Performance measures and worker productivity*. Bonn: IZA World of Labor.
- Shen, Y. & Lei, X. (2022) *Exploring the Impact of Leadership Characteristics on Subordinates' Counterproductive Work Behavior: From the Organizational Cultural Psychology Perspective*. Frontier in Psychology, 13, 818509. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.818509>

Seibert, S.E., Wang, G., & Courtright, S.H. (2011). *Antecedents and Consequences of Psychological and Team Empowerment in Organizations: A Meta-Analytic Review*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(5), 981-1003. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0022676.supp>

Smith, E.F., Gilmer, D.O., & Stockdale, M.S. (2019). *The importance of culture and support for workplace flexibility: An ecological framework for understanding flexibility support structures*. *Business Horizons*, 62(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2019.04.002>.

Sonnentag, S. & Frese, M. (2001). *Performance Concepts and Performance Theory*. Wiley Online Library. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0470013419.ch1>

Suárez-Albanchez, J., Pedro J.E., Juan J. B.R. & Santiago G.B. (2022). *Team Autonomy and Organizational Support, Well-Being, and Work Engagement in the Spain Computer Consultancy Industry: The Mediating Effect of Emotional Intelligence*. *Administrative Sciences*, 12, 85. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci12030085>

Sypniewska, B. (2020). *Counterproductive Work Behavior and Organizational Citizenship Behavior*. *Advances in cognitive psychology*, 16(4), 321–328. <https://doi.org/10.5709/acp-0306-9>

van Eerde, W. (2016). *Procrastination and Well-Being at Work*. In *Procrastination, Health, and Well-being*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.

Veldman, I., van Tartwijk, J., Brekelmans, M., & Wubbels, T. (2013). *Job satisfaction and teacher-student relationships across the teaching career: Four case studies*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 32, 55-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2013.01.005>

Viswesvaran, C. & Ones, D.S. (2000). *Perspectives on models of job performance*. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 8(4), 216-26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2389.00151>

Weideman, M. & Hofmeyr, K.B. (2020). *The influence of flexible work arrangements on employee engagement: An exploratory study*. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v18i0.1209>

West, M.A. (2001). *Organizational Climate*. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. Turkey: Pergamon.

Whiting, S. W., Podsakoff, P.M., & Pierce, J. R. (2008). The effects of task performance, helping, voice, and organizational loyalty on performance appraisal ratings. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(1), 125-139. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.93.1.125>

Wilkinson, D. & Birmingham, P. (2003). *Using Research Instruments A Guide for Researchers*. London: Routledge Falmer.

Woolley, A. W., Aggarwal, I., & Malone, T. W. (2015). Collective intelligence and group performance. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 24, 420-424. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721415599543>

Yedgarian, V.A. (2021). Adverse Effects and Intangible Costs for American Expatriates in Russia. In *Handbook of Research on Institutional, Economic, and Social Impacts of Globalization and Liberalization*. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge.

Zhou, Z. (2020). Counterproductive Work Behavior. *Oxford Bibliographies Online*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OBO/9780199846740-0143>.

Publisher's Note: DWIJMH stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

© 2022 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Divine Word International Journal of Management and Humanities. DWIJMH is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.